

Participating in and satisfaction to basic public health services-based physical examination among community elderly in eastern, central and western China

LI Mengyu, LIAO Zirui, LIAN Juan, LIU Lu, YOU Lili, LIU Yuanli

School of Health Policy and Management, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences & Peking Union Medical College, Beijing 100005, China

Corresponding author: YOU Lili, E-mail: youlily_pumc@163.com

Abstract:

Objective To examine the utilization of and satisfaction to physical examination – one of items in basic public health services among community elderly in eastern, central and western China.

Methods With stratified multi-stage random sampling and a self-designed questionnaire, an onsite interviewer-assisted self-administered survey was conducted among 3 334 elderly attendees (aged 65 years and above) of 20 primary medical institutions during November – December 2019 in eastern, central and western China (Zhejiang province, Shanxi province and Chongqing municipality).

Results Of the 3 213 participants with eligible responses, 3 008 (93.6%) reported ever taking physical examination free of charge at community health service centers or township health centers during past one year. Among the 3 008 participants receiving the physical examination, 2 247 (74.7%) expressed the satisfaction to the check-up items of the physical examination. In terms of expected improvements for the physical examination, inclusion of more check up items was suggested by 49.6% of the participants, followed by increasing the frequency of physical examination, providing a more detailed physical examination report, and timely notification of the physical examination results which were suggested by 15.1%, 14.9%, and 12.3% of the participants, respectively.

Conclusion The utilization ratio of national basic public health services-based physical examination is high among community elderly in China but items and service processes of the physical examination still need to be improved.

Keywords: essential public health services/health examination/utilization rate/satisfaction/elderly people

With the continuous development of the aging process, the number of elderly population in China is increasing. According to the seventh national population census data released by the National Bureau of Statistics, as of November 1, 2020, the population aged ≥ 65 years in China reached 190 million, accounting for 13.5% [1], and population aging is becoming increasingly severe. Studies show that the bodily functions and health levels of older adults decline with age, making them a high-prevalence group for various chronic diseases. Regular

health examinations can effectively monitor the health status of the elderly population and provide appropriate health management based on health data in a timely manner [2].

According to the requirements for elderly health management services in the "National Basic Public Health Service Specifications (Third Edition)" [3], primary healthcare institutions (i.e., community health service centers and township health centers) should provide one health examination per year for permanent residents aged ≥ 65 years in their jurisdictions to timely and effectively carry out subsequent elderly health management and guidance, thereby improving the health levels of older adults. Although the National Health Commission conducts annual project assessments every year, it has not evaluated the effectiveness of basic public health services from a population perspective [4]. To understand the participation and satisfaction of older adults in basic public health health examinations in eastern, central, and western regions of China, providing reference for improving elderly health management in basic public health service projects, this study used a multi-stage stratified sampling method from November to December 2019 to select 3,334 older adults aged ≥ 65 years who visited 20 primary healthcare institutions in Zhejiang Province (eastern region), Shanxi Province (central region), and Chongqing Municipality (western region) for a questionnaire survey. The results are reported as follows.

1 Subjects and Methods

1.1 Subjects

A multi-stage stratified sampling method was adopted. First, based on geographical characteristics, Zhejiang Province, Shanxi Province, and Chongqing Municipality were selected as the first-level sampling units in eastern, central, and western regions of China, respectively. Second, based on the level of economic development, two municipal regions were selected in Zhejiang and Shanxi Provinces as second-level sampling units, and Chongqing, as a municipality directly under the central government, was directly included as a second-level sampling unit. Then, based on the distinction between urban and rural areas, one urban district and one county were selected in each city as third-level sampling units. Finally, based on the different positioning of primary healthcare institutions, two community health service centers/township health centers were selected in each urban district/county, resulting in a total of 20 primary healthcare institutions as survey sites. At each survey site, convenience sampling was used to conduct questionnaire surveys among older adults aged ≥ 65 years visiting for medical care. A total of 3,334 questionnaires were distributed, with 3,213 valid questionnaires recovered, yielding an effective recovery rate of 96.37%. This study was approved by the Ethics Review Committee for Biomedical Research Involving Humans at the Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences & Peking Union Medical College (Approval No.: CAMS&PUMC-IEC-2022-025), and all respondents signed informed consent forms.

1.2 Methods

A self-designed "Demand-Side Survey Questionnaire for National Basic Public Health Services" was used, divided into three versions: general older adults questionnaire, hypertensive older adults questionnaire, and diabetic older adults questionnaire. General older

adults refer to those aged ≥ 65 years who self-reported no hypertension or diabetes but may have other diseases; hypertensive or diabetic older adults refer to those aged ≥ 65 years who self-reported having hypertension or diabetes, respectively. The questionnaire content included: (1) Basic information: gender, age, region, residence, marital status, household registration, and average monthly household income; (2) Utilization of basic public health health examinations: the question was "In the past year, have you participated in a free health examination organized by the community health service center/township health center?"; (3) Awareness of health examination items: "What are the contents of the free health examination you participated in at the community health service center/township health center?"; (4) Satisfaction with elderly health examination items: questions were "Do you think these examination items meet your health needs?" and "Do you have any suggestions or opinions on the current free examinations provided?", where satisfaction with health examination items was divided into "fully met," "met," "average," "not met," and "not met at all." In this study, "fully met" and "met" were calculated as "satisfied" for the satisfaction rate. All questionnaires were self-completed by respondents and collected on-site after uniformly trained investigators explained the survey purpose and filling methods. If respondents were unable to complete them independently for any reason, investigators conducted face-to-face interviews.

1.3 Statistical Analysis

SPSS 20.0 was used for general descriptive analysis and χ^2 tests, with $P < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

2 Results

2.1 General Characteristics

Among the 3,213 older adults aged ≥ 65 years finally included in the analysis from eastern, central, and western regions of China, there were 1,447 males (45.0%), 1,741 females (54.2%), and 25 missing (0.8%); 2,232 aged 65-74 years (69.5%), 845 aged 75-84 years (26.3%), and 136 aged ≥ 85 years (4.2%); 1,251 from eastern regions (38.9%), 1,299 from central regions (40.4%), and 663 from western regions (20.6%); 1,594 residing in urban areas (49.6%) and 1,619 in rural areas (50.4%); 593 not married (18.5%), 2,595 married (80.5%), and 25 missing (0.8%); 2,920 with local household registration (90.9%), 218 with non-local (6.8%), and 75 missing (2.3%); average monthly household income $< 2,000$ yuan for 1,597 (49.7%), 2,000-5,000 yuan for 1,186 (36.9%), $> 5,000$ yuan for 410 (12.8%), and 20 missing (0.6%); 678 general older adults (21.1%), 1,569 hypertensive older adults (48.8%), and 966 diabetic older adults (30.1%).

2.2 Utilization of Basic Public Health Health Examinations Among Older Adults in Eastern, Central, and Western Regions of China (Table 1)

Among the 3,213 older adults finally included in the analysis from eastern, central, and western regions of China, 3,008 utilized basic public health health examinations, with a utilization rate of 93.6%. Comparisons among older adults with different characteristics in eastern, central, and western regions of China showed statistically significant differences in the utilization rates of basic public health service health examinations among older adults

with different residences, marital statuses, and population types (all $P < 0.05$).

2.3 Awareness of Examination Items Among Older Adults Utilizing Basic Public Health Health Examinations

Among older adults utilizing basic public health health examinations in eastern, central, and western regions of China, the awareness rates for routine blood tests, routine urine tests, abdominal ultrasound, electrocardiogram, fasting blood glucose, liver function, blood lipids, and kidney function tests were 96.3% (2,896/3,008), 96.0% (2,888/3,008), 95.9% (2,886/3,008), 95.7% (2,879/3,008), 92.5% (2,783/3,008), 88.0% (2,646/3,008), 87.2% (2,622/3,008), and 83.4% (2,509/3,008), respectively.

2.4 Satisfaction Rates Among Older Adults Utilizing Basic Public Health Health Examinations in Eastern, Central, and Western Regions of China (Table 2)

Among the 3,008 older adults utilizing basic public health health examinations, 2,247 were satisfied, resulting in a satisfaction rate of 74.7%. Comparisons among older adults with different characteristics utilizing basic public health health examinations in eastern, central, and western regions of China showed statistically significant differences in satisfaction rates among older adults with different residences, average monthly household incomes, and population types (all $P < 0.05$).

2.5 Suggestions for Basic Public Health Health Examinations From Older Adults in Eastern, Central, and Western Regions of China

In the suggestions for health examinations from older adults, 49.6% (1,593/3,213) suggested "adding examination items," 15.1% (484/3,213) suggested "increasing examination frequency," 14.9% (480/3,213) suggested "detailed interpretation of examination reports," and 12.3% (395/3,213) suggested "timely notification of examination results."

3 Discussion

Health examinations occupy an important position in national basic public health services, and the country places particular emphasis on health examinations for older adults. Timely and regular health examinations can achieve the "three early" preventions for chronic diseases [5] and help older adults improve their awareness of chronic disease self-management and self-monitoring. To this end, the country provides free basic public health health examination services for older adults aged ≥ 65 years, and since the project's launch, older adults have benefited significantly [6]. The results of this survey show that the utilization rate of basic public health health examinations among older adults in eastern, central, and western regions of China is 93.6%. The possible reasons why the utilization rate among older adults did not reach 100% are, on one hand, that this data is based on the demand side, so older adults may have recall bias and forget that they participated in health examinations; on the other hand, primary healthcare institutions may not have comprehensive promotion and popularization of this national basic public health service, leading to omissions of older adults. Since the country launched a new round of deepening medical and health system reform in 2009, primary healthcare institutions have fully implemented national basic public health service projects, including health management for hypertension and diabetes patients as important

components of chronic disease management [7]. Over the years, services such as health management and health examinations for chronic disease populations have been carried out, and multiple studies have shown that the coverage rates of various basic public health services have increased over the 10 years, and the control rates for hypertension and hyperglycemia patients have also improved [8-10]. The results of this survey show that the utilization rate of basic public health health examinations among general older adults is 90.7%, which is lower than the 94.5% and 94.2% among hypertensive and diabetic older adults, consistent with the findings of Hu Xiyuan et al. [11] that older adults with chronic diseases are more likely to participate in health examinations. This indicates, on one hand, the need to strengthen health promotion for general older adults while reasonably managing chronic disease populations, thereby increasing the utilization rate of basic public health services among general older adults and achieving full population coverage; on the other hand, it suggests that the general older adult group may include individuals with well-controlled hypertension and hyperglycemia, and hypertensive and hyperglycemic older adults, due to having chronic diseases, may generally have higher levels of knowledge about medicine and attention to health examination content than general older adults. Therefore, during follow-ups with chronic disease populations, emphasis should be placed on educating non-chronic disease populations and those with well-controlled blood pressure and blood glucose about the importance of health examinations. The results of this survey also show that the satisfaction rate with health examinations among diabetic older adults (72.4%) is lower than that among hypertensive older adults (77.5%), which may be related to the lower knowledge mastery and disease control rates among diabetic patients after implementing health management compared to hypertensive patients [12]. China's community management system for hypertension populations is very good, with improvements in blood pressure treatment and control levels among hypertensive patients [13], thus excelling in health examination utilization rates and resident satisfaction compared to diabetic populations. To this end, relevant studies suggest increasing health examination rates by strengthening the coverage of education and intensifying chronic disease screening [14].

The results of this survey show that the utilization rate of health examinations among urban older adults is lower than that among rural older adults (92.2% vs 95.0%), and the satisfaction rate with health examinations among urban older adults is also lower than that among rural older adults (72.9% vs 78.9%). This may be because urban older adults often participate in various health knowledge lectures organized by communities, popularization of chronic disease lifestyle and prevention measures, and community volunteer activities [15], thereby to some extent improving urban older adults' mastery of health knowledge, attention to their own health, and ability to access health services. Therefore, urban older adults have richer demands in health aspects, leading to lower satisfaction rates with health examinations compared to rural older adults. At the same time, due to differences in urban-rural economic development levels and social security systems, urban medical accessibility is higher than rural [16], so urban older adults have more choices for health examinations and are not limited to the basic health examinations provided by primary healthcare institutions but seek more detailed examinations [17], leading to lower utilization rates of health examinations among urban older adults compared to rural ones. Therefore, as a national coverage,

population-oriented, and well-funded most basic public health service, national basic public health services should reasonably allocate health resources and provide continuous and regionally equitable medical and health services [18].

In the suggestions for health examinations from older adults, 49.6% suggested "adding examination items," and 15.1% suggested "increasing examination frequency." This also reflects from the demand-side perspective that older adults have strong demands for health examinations, and the current health examination items do not well meet their health needs, so older adults hope to add examination items and frequency. In addition, 14.9% of older adults suggested "detailed interpretation of examination reports," and 12.3% suggested "timely notification of examination results." Meanwhile, the awareness rates of various health examination items among older adults utilizing basic public health health examinations did not reach 100%, indicating that some older adults do not know which examination items they participated in or even the examination results. This is consistent with the suggestions proposed by older adults for the implementation process of national basic public health service health examinations. Therefore, older adults hope to improve the full-process service of health examinations, timely inform and explain the examination results after completion, thereby improving older adults' cognition of their physical condition and actively taking subsequent treatments to improve health status. Therefore, in addition to strengthening the promotion of basic public health services, investments in community health service institutions can be increased to improve the service quality of health examinations, thereby further increasing older adults' utilization rates of basic public health service health examinations.

Due to this study adopting a multi-stage stratified sampling combined with convenience sampling, there is non-random sampling in the sampling process, thus there is certain selection bias in obtaining survey subjects [19]. In addition, the utilization rates and other indicators obtained in this survey are all self-reported by survey subjects, thus there may be reporting bias [20]. Therefore, in future surveys, random sampling or cluster random sampling by region should be adopted as much as possible in sample selection to reduce bias occurrence.

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Table 1 Demographic- and Region-Specific Ratios of Participation in Basic Public Health Services-Based Physical Examination Among 3,334 Community Elderly in Eastern, Central, and Western China

Characteristics	Number Surveyed	Number Utilizing	Utilization Rate (%)	χ^2 Value	P Value
Gender^a				0.183	0.669
Male	1,447	1,351	93.4		
Female	1,741	1,632	93.7		
Age (years)				3.819	0.148
65-74	2,232	2,096	93.9		
75-84	845	790	93.5		
≥85	136	122	89.7		
Region				0.855	0.652
Eastern	1,251	1,169	93.4		
Central	1,299	1,222	94.1		
Western	663	617	93.1		
Residence				10.743	0.001
Urban	1,594	1,493	92.2		
Rural	1,619	1,515	95		
Marital Status^a				5.39	0.02
Unmarried	593	543	91.6		
Married	2,595	2,443	94.1		
Household Registration^a				3.252	0.071
Local	2,920	2,742	93.9		
Non-local	218	198	90.8		
Average Monthly Household Income (¥)^a				5.95	0.051
<2,000	1,597	1,512	94.7		
2,000-5,000	1,186	1,096	92.4		
>5,000	410	383	93.4		
Population Type				12.297	0.002
General Older Adults	678	615	90.7		

Hypertensive Older Adults	1,569	1,483	94.5
Diabetic Older Adults	966	910	94.2

Note: a indicates missing data.

Table 2 Demographic-Specific Ratios of Satisfaction to Basic Public Health Services-Based Physical Examination Among 3,008 Community Elderly Examinees in Eastern, Central, and Western China

Characteristics	Number Utilizing	Number Satisfied	Satisfaction Rate (%)	χ^2 Value	P Value
Gender^a				1.463	0.226
Male	1,351	996	74.9		
Female	1,632	1,233	76.8		
Age (years)				1.339	0.512
65-74	2,096	1,559	75.4		
75-84	790	594	76.8		
≥85	122	94	79		
Region				2.854	0.24
Eastern	1,169	883	77.1		
Central	1,222	919	76		
Western	617	445	73.4		
Residence				14.528	<0.001
Urban	1,493	1,078	72.9		
Rural	1,515	1,169	78.9		
Marital Status^a				0.394	0.53
Unmarried	543	397	74.9		
Married	2,443	1,837	76.2		
Household Registration^a				0.008	0.927
Local	2,742	2,044	75.7		
Non-local	198	149	76		
Average Monthly Household Income (¥)^a				6.142	0.046
<2,000	1,512	1,164	77.7		
2,000-5,000	1,096	793	73.8		
>5,000	383	274	73.9		

Population Type				8.678	0.013
General Older Adults	615	466	77.2		
Hypertensive Older Adults	1,483	1,134	77.5		
Diabetic Older Adults	910	647	72.4		

Note: a indicates missing data.